

THE LANDSLIDE IMPACT IN CHINA

Submit to:

Shuqian Duan

PHD in Geotechnical Engineering,

Assistant professor, School of Civil Engineering, Zhengzhou University, Zhengzhou,
Henan 45001, China.

MD MOSFIKUR ROHAN ;

MOHAMMAD BIPLAB MIA ;

MD KAZI AMIR KHAN

Student of Civil Engineering in Zhengzhou University, Zhengzhou, Henan 45001, China.

Abstract: China is the country with most widely distributed loess area in the world, and its loess area accounts of 6.63% of total nation land area. The landslide disaster occurs frequently for complex natural condition and becomes major factors hindering the social and economic development of loess regions. Through different indexes, the authors divided the landslides into 9 principal types and analyzed the distribution characteristics of loess landslide in time and space, the affecting factors and mechanism of landslides. It is pointed out that time and spatial distributions of landslides are closely correlative to topographic and geomorphic conditions, earthquake and rainfall, and the key influencing factors include topography, geomorphology, new tectonic movements, earthquake activity, surface water, ground water and human activities. The authors emphasized that the natural condition of loess areas was favorable to landslides, human activities impelled its occurrence and that controlling the loess landslide was an urgent task for sustainable development in the loess zone.

Introduction: Landslides, as one of the major natural hazards, account each year for enormous property damage in terms of both direct and indirect costs.

Landslides, defined as the movement of a mass of rock, debris or earth down a slope can be triggered by a variety of external stimulus, such as intense rainfall,

earthquake shaking, water level change, storm waves or rapid stream erosion that cause a rapid increase in shear stress or decrease in shear strength of slope-forming materials. In addition, as development expands into unstable hillslope areas under the pressures of increasing population and urbanization, human activities such as deforestation or excavation of slopes for road cuts and building sites, etc., have become important triggers for landslide occurrence.

1. LANDSLIDE INCIDENT AREA & IMPACT

Here we are discuss about heavy landslide occur in china 2010. So in this case we can take some specific areas like [Guizhou](#), [Jiangxi Province](#), [Fujian Province](#), [Anhui Province](#), [Gansu](#), [Sichuan Province](#), [Hunan Province](#), [Hubei Province](#), [Guangdong Province](#), [Jilin Province](#) , [Liaoning Province](#) , [Heilongjiang Province](#), [Yunnan Province](#), [Hainan Province](#), [Qinghai Province](#), [Chongqing Municipality](#) .

Guizhou Province

After experiencing severe drought, heavy rains triggered a landslide in Guizhou Province around 2:30 pm on June 28 that trapped 99 people in the village of Dazhai, Gangwu Township, Anshun. Ganwu received 257 millimeters of rain on June 27, a record for the township, and the resulting landslide lasted two minutes and unleashed up to 2 million cubic metres (2.6 million cu yd) of mud and rock, burying at least 37 buildings and homes in Dazhai. Officials stated there was little hope for survival of the buried victims, and the torrential rains were likely to continue. The rains hampered rescue efforts in the search for survivors from the 38 families buried by the landslide. Chinese Vice Premier Hui Liangyu urged the use of all resources to rescue any survivors. The first body, a child, was found by rescue workers in the late afternoon of June 29. More than 1,100 rescue workers searched to find the remaining victims, including up to 30 children and infants, and eight of the original missing turned up alive. By July 1, 10 bodies had been found at the site of the landslide, and 89 still missing and feared dead. At least 1,000 people were evacuated from the village in the aftermath of the landslide. A total of 42 bodies were found by June 29, and the remaining 57 missing were presumed dead.

Jiangxi Province

Seventeen levees were breached in Jiangxi and 33,900 water conservancy projects were damaged. The direct economic loss is about 25.5 billion yuan. A 347-metre-wide (1,138 ft) breach of the Changkai dike on the Fuhe River, which burst its banks on June 21 and again on June 23, in Luozhen Township, Fuzhou City, forced 1.32 million people to evacuate. The breach was repaired on June 27. The local and provincial government provided tents, quilts,

blankets, clothing and water dispensers to the affected residents. The flood crest of the Gan River passed the city of Nanchang on June 23. Residents of the city of Ganzhou were protected from the flooding by drains built in the area during the Song Dynasty.

Fujian Province

In Fujian, 400 victims of flooding were safely transferred and properly rehoused. Seventy-six people were killed and 79 were missing from landslides in the province by June 21. The village of Baozhuang was completely cut off for six days before rescue workers brought the residents to safety. More than ten consecutive days of rain hit Nanping, and factories were destroyed. The number of people affected was totalled at 1.3 million, damages totalled 5.5 billion yuan, and 365,000 people were relocated.[29] Flooding destroyed a bridge in the province on July 7, travel was disrupted in 20 counties and the town of Taining was completely under water at one point.

Guangxi Autonomous Region

34.96 million people in Guangxi were affected, 37 deaths, 164.58 thousand hectares of crops affected, 16,395 residential housings collapsed. The direct economic loss is about 24.0543 million yuan, of which 10.2081 million were agricultural losses.

Anhui Province

At least four million people have been affected in Anhui Province. 5,100 houses have collapsed, and a further 17,700 houses were damaged.

Gansu Province

Main article: 2010 Gansu mudslide Landslides in Zhugqu County, Gannan Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture in Gansu Province late in the night on August 7 buried Yueyuan Village, a village of 300 families, killing 1,435 people, and leaving 330 others missing. The landslide buried half of Chengguan Township, the county seat, surrounding the village with water and destroying an area 5 kilometres (3.1 mi) long, 500 metres (1,600 ft) wide and 2 metres (6 ft 7 in) deep before water levels receded. About 45,000 people were evacuated from the site, and 1,243 others were rescued by the army and local residents. Excavators and large rescue vehicles were not able to reach the scene because of landslides and floodwaters. Premier Wen Jiabao arrived in the county at 4:35 pm on August 8. A power outage following the slide covered two-thirds of the county. The Bailong River was dammed by the landslide and started to overflow around 1 am on August 8, creating a landslide lake 3 kilometres (1.9 mi) long, 100 metres (330 ft) wide and 9 metres (30 ft) deep, holding 1.5 million m³ of water and submerging parts of the town, forcing 19,000 people downstream.

Demolition experts started working on the lake to release some of its water. The death toll continued to rise, and more rain fell in the area afterwards, hampering relief efforts. A rare national day of mourning was held in China to remember the victims of the Gansu mudslide on August 15. There was speculation that the approximately 1,700 people made homeless by the landslides and relocated would have to spend the winter in tents.

Sichuan Province

The flooding affected 31.81 million people in Sichuan, including Luzhou city's 95 townships. The direct economic loss of Luzhou was about 132 million yuan. The total direct economic loss was about 6.89 billion yuan, and 25,000 homes were damaged in the flooding in August. A landslide in the village of Wangong, Hanyuan County, left 21 people missing after burying 58 homes on July 27 and forcing 4,000 to evacuate. In Mianzhu and Deyang, heavy rains started on August 12 and landslides hit on August 13, killing five people and trapping 500 more in an area devastated by the recent drought and the earthquake in 2008. Sixteen people were dead after the flooding and mudslides since August 13. Sixty-six were declared missing, by August 20,[49] including at least 38 in Wenchuan County, Ten thousand people were forced to evacuate.[62] Further landslides killed 18 people, injured nine and left four missing in Wenchuan and Qingchuan County.[63] Landslides created a flood lake in Yingxing Township, and floodwaters 4 metres (13 ft) deep covered a 200 metres (660 ft) stretch of the only highway that links Wenchuan and Chengdu.

Hunan Province

People in 14 cities in Hunan were affected, and 25,300 houses collapsed at the time of the report. The province experienced its worst flooding since 2003.[19] In late June, floodwaters threatened the major city of Changsha, as water levels rose 2.5 metres (8 ft 2 in) above danger level, the highest in a decade, and the third-highest since 1953.

Hubei Province

In Hubei, the Han River at Wuhan experienced its worst flooding in twenty years, as officials continued sandbagging efforts along the Han and Yangtze River Henan Province.

In the city of Luoyang, Henan, a bridge on the Yi River collapsed as onlookers crowded it to watch the flooding, 51 people were killed with 15 missing. Flooding also threatened the Longmen Grottoes, a UNESCO World Heritage Site in the city.

Guangdong Province

In Huilai County in Guangdong, 604 millimetres (23.8 in) of rain fell in six hours, the fastest rainfall accumulation recorded there in approximately 50 years. Three deaths occurred in the province with two missing, while 550,000 people were affected and 80,000 relocated.

Jilin Province

Eighty-five people died in Jilin Province, and 71 went missing due to floods. Jilin was one of the worst-hit regions in China due to rain and landslides since July 20. Flooding first started in June, and over 1,000,000 people were evacuated in the province since July, a record for the province, more than four million were affected. Sixty-two thousand houses were destroyed and 193,000 damaged, while direct economic losses reached 45 billion yuan. On July 28, several thousand barrels from two chemical plants in Jilin City were washed into the Songhua River by the floods. The barrels contained toxic chemicals like trimethylsilyl chloride and hexamethyldisiloxane, with each barrel holding about 170 kilograms (370 lb). There were reports that some barrels exploded on contact with water. The Dahe Dam in Changshan Township, Huadian City was breached on July 28, spilling 4 million cubic metres (140 million cu ft) of water, destroying five villages downstream and leaving 40 people dead or missing.[70] By late afternoon on August 1, 6,387 barrels had been retrieved from the river. Officials stated that tests showed the water in the river remained safe to drink. Three soldiers of the People's Liberation Army in Jilin drowned after working to remove the barrels and control the flooding. In the city of Baishan, near the border with North Korea, an island of garbage covering 15,000 square metres (160,000 sq ft) blocked water flow upstream from the Yunfeng Dam after it became clogged at a bridge. Forty truckloads of garbage were collected, and the remaining garbage could fill 200 more. In Tonghua, 300,000 residents were left without tap water after the flooding damaged major water pipelines that were subsequently repaired by August 4.[67] In addition, 15,702 residents from Liuhe County in Tonghua were evacuated to safer locations by August 5. Unprecedented record levels of flooding hit the Yalu River, where shipping was suspended, and the Tumen River both bordering North Korea, while Yanbian Korean Autonomous Prefecture in the province suffered its worst flooding in one hundred years. In Linjiang City, also bordering North Korea on the Yalu, three townships were cut off by floods and mudslides, and 38,000 residents were relocated. Between July 31 and August 4, 68,000 residents were without drinking water due to flooding, until it was restored at 5 p.m. on August 4 but the water was not potable until approximately August 7. Fire trucks were mobilized to provide drinking water from nearby springs. In Antu County, 70 homes in one village were destroyed by flooding, a mountain valley was submerged by floods 20 metres (66 ft) deep, forcing 570 families to evacuate. Damages from the floods in the county exceeded 800 million yuan, equal to about

5.7 times the county government's revenue in 2009.[73] In central Jilin, 204 millimetres (8.0 in) of rain fell in 24 hours after August 4, while 121 millimetres (4.8 in) fell in a few hours in Lishu on August 5. Seven of the 25 medium and large reservoirs in Jilin City were forced to discharge, including Fengman Reservoir, the largest reservoir on the Songhua, at a rate of 4,500 cubic metres (160,000 cu ft). A 24-hour monitoring system was set up on many reservoirs. Workers started repairing fifty-one damaged small reservoirs and fortifying

riverbanks in the province after the Songhua River surged to levels twice as high as normal. Premier Wen Jiabao visited Yongji County during the first week of August. Other areas of Northern and Northeastern China received flooding rains, including Liaoning, Heilongjiang, Nei Mongol, Hebei and Shandong.

Liaoning Province

Flooding on the Yalu River in Liaoning affected the city of Dandong in early August. Provincial authorities suspended shipping on the river and more than 40,000 people were evacuated from the city. Heavy rains brought shipping to a halt by August 19, and on August 21 the Yalu breached its banks. About 250,000 people in northeastern China were evacuated, including 94,000 in Dandong, where four people were killed and one missing in Kuandian Manchu Autonomous County. The rain and flooding cut rail services and destroyed more than 200 houses. At least 1,200 people were trapped by flood water.

Rainfall up to 250 millimetres (9.8 in) in 24 hours was expected on August 23.[81] Water levels at one station in Dandong rose 2.5 metres (8.2 ft) above the warning level, the second-highest measurement since 1934.

Heilongjiang Province

The State Flood Control and Drought Relief headquarters warned that flooding and landslides were expected to continue in the Songliao Basin (surrounding the Daqing Field) near the Songhua River in Heilongjiang Province.

Yunnan Province

Malong County in Yunnan was hit by torrential rainfall lasting seven hours, completely filling a nearby reservoir, which then submerged the county. Water over roads was as deep as 1.5 metres (4.9 ft) 1.5 metres. The flooding killed one person and injured 165 others, and 55,000 people were affected in the county while 6,000 houses were destroyed. In Puladi Township, Gongshan, a landslide in June killed 11 people at a hydropower station construction site. On August 18, another landslide containing 600,000 cubic metres (780,000 cu yd) of mud and rock cut off a town after roads and power lines were severed, killing 29 people and leaving 63 missing, as well as injuring 25 people, 9 of them seriously.

Some of the people missing were workers for an iron mine.

Qinghai Province

Torrential rains killed 25 people in Qinghai in July and left three more missing, affecting 41,000 people. The Wenquan Reservoir in the province, 130 kilometres (81 mi) upstream from Golmud, was overfilled with 230 million cubic metres (300 million cu yd) of water, while it was only designed to hold 70 million cubic metres (92 million cu yd), creating a water level 1.18 metres (1.29 yd) above the warning line.[24] Soldiers and rescue workers

built drainage channels to pipe the water away from the reservoir, which would have flooded Golmud with water over 4 metres (4.4 yd) deep if its dam burst, and the channels are designed to release 400 cubic metres (520 cu yd) of water per second. More than 11,300 people were evacuated from the city.

Hainan Province

Starting from September 30 Hainan Province received the worst flooding in half a century. By October 7 the flood killed one, left three missing, and affected 1.65 million people in 16 cities and counties.

Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region

By August, heavy rains and snow melt in Xinjiang caused water levels in the region's 13 major rivers to rise above danger levels. In Aksu Prefecture, roads were cut off and bridges destroyed, while 1,000 people became trapped in the mountainous areas. On August 1, helicopters rescued 118 of the trapped people and delivered relief goods to the remaining residents. Floods triggered by torrential rains pounded Akto County on July 6 resulted in 6 deaths and 2 missing.[87] On the morning of August 17, a 540-metre-long (590 yd) bridge spanning the Yarkand River was destroyed by the mountain torrents, incurring a regional block of National Highway 315.

Chongqing Municipality

In July, 10 people were killed in Chongqing and two left missing by July 9. The direct economic damages from the floods in the city were 1.09 billion yuan, and 92 flights were delayed due to the floods. in the city and checked reservoirs.

2. Geographical and geological setting in china.

2.1 Topography

Topography basically determines the gravity on slopes. China's topography is complicated and diversified, high in the west and low in the east. The western land is mainly covered with vast plateaus and towering mountains, and the eastern land mainly consists of undulating hills and flat plains. The terrain gradually descends from west to east like a three terrace staircase (Fig.1). The first terrace is Qinghai-Tibet Plateau with an average elevation of more than 4000m, dropping to the elevation of 1000-2000m in the second terrace. The third terrace includes the Greater Khingan Mountain and the east of Yunnan-

Guizhou Plateau, averaging below the elevation of 500m above sea level. In the high mountainous areas, the incision of terrain is intense and the potential energy increases with the slope gradient, thus the slope is comparatively instable and large-scale landslides are concentrated here.

However, in the low hilly areas, the scale of landslides becomes smaller. Large-scale landslides in China are mostly concentrated in the transitional zone between the first two steps, where the incision of rivers is very strong.

2.2 Tectonics

Tectonics is one of the necessities for landslides development, and the faults determine the scale and Geomorphologic division zones in China. concentration of landslides. found that most giant landslides are very close to the major fault zones in China, particularly the active earthquake zones (Fig.2). This illustrates that these tectonic zones have offered favorable settings for the landslides, and have controlled their regional distribution patterns. Huang et al. [23–25] gave the distribution of landslides triggered by Wenchuan earthquake, showing the feature of zonal distribution along the seismic faults.

2.3 Lithology

Both lithology and geological structure impact the formation of landslides. In China, landslides are likely to happen in 13 kinds of strata, as listed in (Table 1). Clayey soil landslides are concentrated in Chengdu Plain, Sichuan Province, and a few can be found in the middle and downstream of Yangtze River and Northeast China. Hypabyssal rock and clay landslides are concentrated in Qinghai, Gansu, Sichuan, Yunnan and Shanxi provinces. Some loess landslides are observed in the downstream of Yellow River and Qinghai Province. Landslides in mudstone, phyllite and sandy slate are widely distributed in provinces such as Hunan, Hubei, Tibet, Yunnan, Sichuan and Gansu.

2.4,Climate

As territory and topography are diversified with the combination of temperature and rainfall, Mainland China can be generally classified into 5 zones, as shown in Fig.3. Both northwestern Xinjiang Uygur

Autonomous Region and Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region are of temperate continental climate, with sparse rainfall and few landslides. Thenortheast belongs to thtemperate monsoon climate zone, with little rainfall and few landslides. The west belongs to Qinghai-Tibet Plateau cold climate, with high insolation and low temperature. The average elevation is more than 4000m. The rainfall is not abundant and mainly concentrated in the southeast area of this region. The landslides in this region are mainly resultant from ice-snow melt water and glacier-lake outburst flood. The east and the middle belong to subtropical monsoon climate zone with enriched rainfall, and the landslides are mainly distributed in this region.

2.5 Hydrology and rainfall

The current climatic conditions in the study area are featured as a mean daily temperature between 12.0 and 19.7 degree and annual precipitation of 580-850 mm. Rainfall occurs during the monsoon from (April to October) and contributes about 90–96% of the total annual rainfall. Heavy rainfall is mainly concentrated from June to August. with an aspect of 240 degree and a terrain gradient of 30 degree respectively. The upper slope forms a gentle platform due to the early slide in this area.

Rock/soil	Type of rock and soil	Distribution area	Development characters of landslides
Clayey soil	Chengdu clay	Chengdu Plain	Concentrated
	Xiashu clay	The Yangtze River's middle and lower reaches	Thinly distributed
	Red clay	Central South of China, Fujian, Zhejiang, west of Shanxi, north of Shaanxi, Henan	Relatively concentrated
	Black clay	Northeast of China	Thinly distributed
Hypabyssal rocks	Loess	Middle reaches of the Yellow River, and north of China	Concentrated
	Claystone of Gonghe group	Qinghai	Very concentrated
	Claystone of Xigeda group	West of Sichuan	Very concentrated
Diagenesis diagenism	Varicoloured claystone	Shanxi	Very concentrated
	Mudstone and sand-shale	Southwest of China and Shanxi	Concentrated
	Coal measure strata	Southwest of China	Concentrated
	Sandy slate	Hunan, Hubei, Tibet, Yunnan and Sichuan	Relatively concentrated
	Phyllite	Northwest of Sichuan and south of Gansu	Concentrated
	Magmatic rock	Fujian	Very concentrated Relatively concentrated

Table 1 The main slip-easy strata in Mainland China

3 Distribution of landslides in China.

3.1 General distribution of landslides

In 1999, MLR put into operation the “monitoring and preventing by masses” network constructed in 1 640 counties, which have suffered serious losses due to landslides. The term, monitoring and preventing by masses, means that the residents in the landslide-prone areas are mobilized to report the latest recorded landslide to the superior administration. Since 2001, MLR has been collecting the landslides reported every year and announced them to the public, including information on the number of landslides, life loss and property loss. In 2004, MLR began to publish the general information of landslides across the country in each quarter; since 2008, MLR has been publishing the distribution figures of landslides and basic information of large-scale landslides that caused the death of more than 10 persons every month. Figure 4 is the distribution map of landslides occurring during 2004 to 2009, in which 196 894 landslides were included. From Fig.4, it is observed that the distribution of landslides in China is predominately determined by weather and terrain. Taking Qinling Mountains as the border, there are more landslides in the south than those in the north. Separated by the Greater Khingan Mountains, Taihang Mountains and the eastern margin of the Yunnan—Guizhou Plateau, there are more landslides in the west than those in the east. Landslides are concentrated in Yunnan, Guizhou, Sichuan and Chongqing in Southwestern China; Shaanxi, Hubei, Hunan, Jiangxi provinces in central China; and Zhejiang, Fujian, Guangdong and Anhui provinces in Eastern China. In addition, there are a small number of landslides in provinces such as Hebei, Shandong, Jiangsu, Xinjiang Uygur Autonomous Region and Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region.

Figure 1 The climate regionalization in China

Figure 2 Distribution of landslides occurring from 2004 to 2009 in China

Figure 3 Distribution of catastrophic landslides in China since the 20th Century

Fig.4 The average annual precipitation for previous years in China (the data of average annual precipitation are from

<http://www.beimap.com/newmap/map-jmooqqomfno>).

Fig.5 The distribution of rainfall and catastrophic landslides in different months.

Earthquake	Time	Magnitude	Landslide number	Area affected by landslides (km ²)
Loma Prieta, California, USA	1989-10-17	M_w 6.9	1 280	15 000
Racha, Georgia, USA	1991-04-29	M_w 6.9	1 000	3 000
Chi-Chi, Taiwan, China	1999-09-21	M_w 7.5	10 000	3 750
Avaj, Iran	2002-06-22	M_w 6.5	550	3 600
Mid Niigata prefecture, Japan	2004-10-23	M_w 6.6	1 353	276
Kashmir	2005-10-08	M_w 7.6	2 252	7 500
Wenchuan, China	2008-05-12	M_w 8.0	50 000	100 000

Table 2 Earthquake-triggered landslides in the last 20 years.

4. Landslide-prone analysis

4.1 Areas of high frequency of landslides

Based on the distribution of 200 catastrophic landslides since 1900 and conditions of topography, rock types, tectonics, earthquake, rainfall and human activities, China's landslide distribution area can be roughly divided into 12 areas (Fig.7).

1. Eastern Qinghai—Tibet Plateau — western Yunnan Province (Hengduan Mountains area)
2. Western and northwestern Sichuan Province
3. Northeastern Yunnan Province
4. Eastern Sichuan Province
5. Three Gorges reservoir area
6. Southern Shaanxi—northern Sichuan Province (Qinling—Daba Mountain area)
7. Northern Shaanxi—eastern Gansu Province (Loess Plateau area)
8. Eastern Qinghai—middle of Gansu Province (upstream of Yellow River area)
9. Northwestern Hubei Province
10. Western Hunan Province
11. Western and northern Guizhou Province
12. Eastern hilly area

Figure 6 : Distribution areas of high-frequent landslides in China and their susceptibility.

5. Impact of Landslides on Biodiversity and Cropland Abandonment.

Landslides are closely related with loss of biodiversity., landslides are a product of their environment and in return they also influence their environment. Landslides are caused by combination of natural and human factors, while landslides, in return, devastate large area under forests, grassland or bare land, which is the loss of habitat of number of endangered and threatened species. Devastation of forests and grasslands is the loss of flora Sometimes animals are killed due to landslides. During last three decades, landslides and avalanches have increased tremendously due to which biodiversity loss has also increased in the reserve. On the basis of field investigations and discussion with concerned scientists and villagers, it was concluded that it is not the occurrence of landslides only that influence the biodiversity but biodiversity itself influences the landslide pattern too.

The criteria to classify landslides as natural and human-induced were the degree of influence of human activities. The landslides, which are near the man-made structures such as road, villages and dam, were called human-induced landslides.

The landslides, which are far away from every human activity and in natural environment, were termed natural landslides. About 40 landslide and about 17 avalanche sites were investigated during the field investigations, while rock fall is a common phenomena along the roads and rivers.

5.1 Land slide Affects of Human Life

Landslides and Sinkholes in China

- Mudslides and flooding are common in China's mountainous areas, killing hundreds of people every year. Deforestation has led to soil erosion and made some parts of China prone to mudslides after strong rains.
- According to the Guinness Book of Records, the deadliest landslide ever killed 180,000 people in Gansu Province on December 16, 1920. It was caused by a powerful earthquake.
- In September 2003, 12 people were killed when a landslide buried a group of cave houses in the village of Liangjiagou in Shaanxi Province. Most of the dead were in one cave house that was hosting a party for family members after the birth of a son.
- In May 2003, 35 construction workers who were building a highway in Guizhou Province were killed when they were buried under a landslide that occurred after heavy rain.
- In 2003, 100 villagers in southern Guangdong were forced to evacuate their homes when the earth under their community suddenly began to sink. Houses split and

compassed around the village of Ticken as about 30,000 square meters of earth caved in. The largest sunken area was about 10 square meters and sunk to a depth of about five meters. It is believed that underground streams and caves beneath the community caused the subsidence.

- In June 2003, torrential rains and landslides in southern China left at least 148 people dead and caused \$730 million in damage.
- In July 2003, a massive landslide in Sichuan Province left at least 52 people dead. The landslide was caused by flash floods.
- Landslides kill between 800 and 1,000 people a year. Many of the deaths are in Asia, where large numbers of people live in landslide-prone areas. Landslides generally occur on steep, unstable slopes after intense and extreme rainfalls. There are concerns that global warming could increase the risks of landslides.
- In June 2008, 19 workers in a brick factory in Luliang city in northern China were killed when a landslide engulfed their factory.
- In August 2009, 20 people went missing after a massive landslide blocked the Dadu River in Sichuan Province and threatened a hydro-electric dam.
- In November 2008, a mudslide near Chuxiong city in Yunnan Province left 15 dead and 34 missing. It wasn't clear what caused the landslide as there were no reports of heavy rain in the region.

Landslides and Mudslides in 2010

- In the summer of 2010, scores were left missing after torrential rains triggered massive landslides in southern and western China. A massive landslide covered all but the tallest buildings in Ulandi township, a remote mountain community in Yunnan Province, and more than 100 people were killed.
- In March 2010, 27 people were killed by a landslide in a remote part of Shaanxi Province near the village of Shuabfuyi. Most of the dead were in 25 houses that were buried when a mountainside came crashing down on them. One 20-year-old man miraculously was rescued after being buried for 54 hours. His 17-year-old sister was also rescued but she died from her injuries.
- In mid August 2010, 35 people were killed, 295 were injured and more than 6,000 homes collapsed in floods caused by heavy rains in Gansu Province near the area where hundreds were killed by a mudslide. A few days before 32 people were reported missing from landslides triggered by heavy rains in Sichuan Province.

Massive Mudslide in Gansu in 2010 Kills 1,750

In August 2010, over 1,750 people were killed by mudslides triggered by heavy rains that swept through villages in the Zhouqu district of Gansu Province in northwest China. Three villages were swallowed up by waves of mud and rubble-strewn water.

Hundreds of homes, including every structure in one village were completely buried. People died in four-story high buildings that were completely engulfed by mud. [Source: AP and Reuters]

About 134,000 people, most of them Tibetans, live in the Zhouqu District. The Bailong River which runs through the region swelled with rain and jumped its banks and was blocked by debris from the mudslides. Mudslides swept down the tributary valleys that ran into the Bailong River. The town of Zhouqu, which the river runs through, was one-third underwater.

More than 45,000 people were forced to evacuate their homes. Many of these people were put up in tents trucked in by the government. Rescue efforts were hampered by heavy rains that continued to fall after the mudslides. Additional mudslides killed dozens more people, blocked roads bringing relief supplies and made life miserable for people living in tents and shelters.

A debris dam that was blocking the river, creating a dangerous artificial lake that could have burst through dam at any moment, was breached and drained with explosives. Providing clean drinking water was a primary concern as local sources were either knocked out or too polluted for consumption.

Numerous cases of dysentery were reported.

In some houses, everyone was killed. Bodies were wrapped in blankets and tied to sticks or placed on planks and on debris-filled streets for pick up. A few people were rescued several days after the mudslides when they were pulled out of mud-enveloped homes.

Much of the rescue work was done by hand with simple tools such as shovels, hoes and ropes as it was initially too difficult to get heavy equipment into the area. Chinese Premier Wen Jiabao arrived quickly to the scene to comfort survivors and offer moral support to rescuers.

One survivor making coffins told AP, "These are all for relatives killed in the mudslide. It was unexpected---a huge landslide like this. There's nothing left. We managed to escape with our lives. As for relatives, 10 to 20 died from my village."

Some blamed the disaster on heavy tree-felling and rapid hydro development which made regions such as the one struck by the mudslides in Gansu vulnerable to flooding, landslides and mudslides. Government reports released in 2009 said work needed to be done to protect areas deemed "high-occurrence disaster zones for landslides." In addition, soils, geological strata and mountain slopes in the region are said to have been weakened by the huge 2008 Sichuan earthquake, whose epicenter was not far from Zhouqu.

China Landslide Topples School, Buries 18 Students in 2012

In October 2012, Associated Press reported: "A landslide toppled an elementary school building and buried 18 students in a mountainous southwest China county recovering from a recent earthquake. The landslide smothered the Youfang Elementary School and hit two farmhouses in Zhenhe village around 8 a.m., the Yiliang county government said on its website. Another person was buried in a house. [Source: AP, October 4, 2012]"

Rescuers rushed from the Yiliang county seat to Zhenhe three hours away to dig out the students, said an official with the county foreign affairs office, Peng Hong. Rain has lashed the region of mountains and sheer valleys, though Peng said the cause of the landslide was not yet known. Yiliang was struck by an earthquake last month that killed 81 people and devastated several villages. Though Thursday was a holiday across China, students were in school to make up for days missed after the quakes, Peng said.

Nineteen Children among 46 Dead in Yunnan Landslide in January 2013

In January 2013, AFP reported: "A desperate search for three people missing in a landslide in southwestern China ended on Saturday when their bodies were pulled from the mud, taking the final death toll to 46 -- many of them children. Authorities in Yunnan province said that the last three bodies were recovered on Saturday morning after a night of frantic efforts by more than 1,000 rescue workers to locate the final missing residents of the remote village of Gaopo. Xinhua said those buried included 27 adults and 19 children. Authorities said families will receive 20,000 yuan (\$3,200) in compensation for each victim. Two other people were hospitalised after the landslide struck on Friday morning, engulfing 16 homes, bringing a thunderous crash and throwing up thick clouds of dust, the official Xinhua news agency said. [Source: AFP, January 13, 2013]"

Rescuers toiled into the night, braving bitter wind and freezing temperatures, using lamps and specialised detection devices in the hope of locating the missing, Xinhua said. Soldiers, police, firefighters and mine rescue workers joined the search operation, using 20 excavators and trucks, it added. Li Yongju, 50, said she heard the crash of the landslide while cleaning her yard and rushed with other villagers to the disaster site with shovels and hoes. "We pulled out several people, one of whom was breathing weakly. But after a while, he died," Xinhua quoted Li as saying. Zhou Benju, wept as she recounted hearing the rumble of the landslide. "Several relatives of my parents -- my grandma, brother, uncle and my aunt's family members, died," she told the agency.

The landslide was caused by 10 days of heavy rain and snow, steep slopes, unstable soil, and earthquakes that jolted the area in September, according to local geological

experts, Xinhua reported. The area may also have been weakened by the presence of a nearby coalmine, the daily Chongqing Chenbao said, although this was denied by a local official at a press conference broadcast on national television. The area has experienced unusually low temperatures in recent weeks during what authorities have called China's coldest winter in 28 years.

The landslide spread over an area 120 metres (yards) long, 110 metres wide and 16 metres deep, according to authorities. Photos on Yunnan Web, run by the Yunnan provincial government, showed rescuers in orange uniforms digging into wide swathes of mud against a backdrop of snow-covered, terraced hills. A video posted on a Chinese social networking site appeared to show a group of villagers digging through thick mud and debris to uncover a body, which was carried away on a stretcher.

Gaopo is in Zhenxiong county, in the northeast of Yunnan, a temperate province known for its tobacco industry and for being the home of Pu'er tea. But its mountainous areas are prone to landslides and earthquakes. Two quakes in September -- one of magnitude 5.7 -- left 81 dead and hundreds injured. A neighbouring county was hit by a landslide in October that killed 18 children, after one that killed 216 people in 1991, (according to the United States Geological Survey.)

4.2 Impacts of Landslides on Cropland Abandonment

In China, the mountainous area has become an area of simultaneous landslides and cropland abandonment. Mountainous areas represent 70% of China's land area and are the main area prone to natural hazards. Many mountain settlements are located in areas of landslides and suffer from landslides. In 2016, 7403 landslides occurred in China (accounting for 76.2% of the total number of geological disasters). Furthermore, rural areas in China's mountainous areas also experience serious cropland abandonment.

Cropland abandonment arises from the shortage of agricultural laborers. In 2014, approximately 14.32% of the cropland in mountainous areas was abandoned. In summary, landslides and cropland abandonment may have similar spatial agglomeration characteristics in mountainous areas. Therefore, the spatial distribution characteristics of landslides and cropland abandonment in China are still unknown. In fact, the relationship between land use and the distribution of landslides has been a hotspot in the research on agricultural economics and geography. In general, the relief and precipitation are the key drivers of landslides. In mountainous areas, under the background of heavy relief and precipitation, most studies consider that changes in land use may be direct drivers of landslides. Cropland is the largest land use type of human landscape. In the short term, cropland abandonment can easily lead to landslides by altering surface runoff. Conversely, landslides may easily destroy infrastructure which would cause farmers to abandon cropland. However, few studies have quantitatively identified the microscopic impacts of landslides on cropland abandonment using peasant household survey data.

To explore the quantitative impact of landslides on cropland abandonment, this study divided cropland abandonment into abandonment behavior and abandoned area. In Table 2, the dependent variable of the Probit regression models, Models (1)–(3), is abandonment behavior (abbreviated to Behavior). In addition, in Table 2, the dependent variable of the Tobit regression models, Models (5)–(7), is the abandoned area (abbreviated to Area). The identification strategy of this study was to gradually introduce control variables and observe whether the focal variable is significant and stable. Additionally, because the probit and Tobit methods are nonlinear estimates, their estimation results cannot be directly used as quantitative coefficients. Thus, the quantitative coefficients are estimated by marginal effect estimation based on Models (3) and (7) for the Probit model and the Tobit model, respectively. As shown in Table 2, in Model (1), only the focal variable Landslide is introduced; in Model (2), the province dummy variables are introduced on the basis of Model (1) to exclude estimation bias arising from geographical differences; in Model (3), the characteristics of householder, household and social environment are introduced on the basis of Model (2) to exclude estimation bias arising from other factors; Model (4) presents the marginal estimated results based on Model (3). In Models (1)–(3), the focal variable Landslide is always significant at a level of 1%, which is greater than zero. The results reveal that landslides are the determinant driving cropland abandonment. Based on the results of Model (4), Landslide has a positive and significant sign and a coefficient of 0.068. The results reveal that, if a farmer suffers from landslides, his probability of abandoning cropland will increase by 6.8% after keeping all other variables unchanged. Additionally, the control variables of Age, Employment and Off-farm income are significantly and positively correlated with Behavior, while the control variables of Elder and Urbanization are significantly and negatively correlated with Behavior. More specifically, keeping other variables unchanged, for every one-year increase in Age, the probability of cropland abandonment increases by 0.2%; for every 1% increase in Employment, the probability of cropland abandonment increases by 0.1%; for every 1% increase in Off-farm income, the probability of cropland abandonment increases by 3.4%; if elderly members of the household (over 64 years old) are engaged in agricultural production, the probability of cropland abandonment decreases by 2.9%; and for every 1% increase in Urbanization, the probability of cropland abandonment decreases by 0.1%. As shown in Table 2, in Model (5), only the focal variable Landslide is introduced; in Model (6), the province dummy variables are introduced on the basis of Model (5) to exclude estimation bias arising from geographical differences; in Model (7), the characteristics of householder, household and social environment are introduced on the basis of Model (6) to exclude estimation bias arising from other factors; and Model (8) presents the marginal estimated results based on Model (7). In Models (5)–(7), the focal variable Landslide is always significant at a level of 1%, which is greater than zero. The results also reveal that landslides are the determinant driving cropland abandonment. Based on the results of Model (8), Landslide has a positive and significant sign, and a coefficient of 0.064. The results reveal that if a farmer suffers from landslides, his area of abandoning cropland will increase by 0.064 mu after keeping other variables unchanged. Additionally, the control variables of Sustainability 2018, 10, 3909 8 of 14 Age, Employment, Land size and Off-farm income are significantly and positively correlated with Area; the control

variables of Elder and Urbanization are significantly and negatively correlated with area. More specifically, keeping other variables unchanged, for every one-year increase in Age, the area of cropland abandonment increased by 0.002 mu; for every 1% increase in Employment cropland abandonment increases by 0.001 mu; for every 1 mu increase in Land size, the area of cropland abandonment increases by 0.001 mu; for every 1% increase in Off-farm income, the area of cropland abandonment increases by 0.031 mu; if elderly members of the household (over 64 years old) are engaged in agricultural production, the area of cropland abandonment decreases by 0.031 mu; and for every 1% increase in Urbanization, the area of cropland abandonment decreases by 0.001 mu.

Table 2. Econometric model estimation results of cropland abandonment in mountain area ^a.

	Dependent Variable: Behavior				Dependent Variable: Area			
	Model (1)	Model (2)	Model (3)	Model (4)	Model (5)	Model (6)	Model (7)	Model (8)
Landslide	0.284 *** (0.048)	0.333 *** (0.055)	0.325 *** (0.057)	0.068 *** (0.012)	1.586 *** (0.361)	1.749 *** (0.397)	1.661 *** (0.378)	0.064 *** (0.010)
Age			0.010 *** (0.002)	0.002 *** (0.000)			0.052 *** (0.011)	0.002 *** (0.000)
Education			0.030 (0.077)	0.006 (0.016)			0.336 (0.398)	0.013 (0.015)
Employment			0.003 *** (0.001)	0.001 *** (0.000)			0.015 *** (0.003)	0.001 *** (0.000)
Household size			0.007 (0.012)	0.001 (0.003)			0.056 (0.063)	0.002 (0.003)
Elder			-0.139 * (0.078)	-0.029 * (0.016)			-0.812 ** (0.377)	-0.031 ** (0.014)
Land size			0.009 (0.006)	0.002 (0.001)			0.107 ** (0.050)	0.004 ** (0.002)
Land right			0.061 (0.053)	0.013 (0.011)			0.166 (0.249)	0.006 (0.009)
Off-farm income			0.164 *** (0.060)	0.034 *** (0.012)			0.807 *** (0.308)	0.031 *** (0.011)
Fixed assets			-0.004 (0.004)	-0.001 (0.001)			-0.021 (0.021)	-0.001 (0.001)
Agricultural assets			-0.060 (0.134)	-0.013 (0.028)			-0.812 (0.736)	-0.031 (0.027)
Distance			0.000 (0.002)	0.000 (0.000)			0.002 (0.010)	0.000 (0.000)
Urbanization			-0.007 *** (0.001)	-0.001 *** (0.000)			-0.027 *** (0.007)	-0.001 *** (0.000)
Constant	-1.141 *** (0.027)	-0.674 *** (0.227)	-1.250 *** (0.269)		-6.611 *** (0.906)	-2.698 * (1.456)	-6.121 *** (1.703)	
Province dummies	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observation	4850	4850	4850	4850	4850	4850	4850	4850

^a Robust standard errors in parentheses; * Significant at $\alpha = 0.10$; ** significant at $\alpha = 0.05$; *** significant at $\alpha = 0.01$.

5. Landslide risk assessment and management

5.1 Basic framework for landslide risk assessment and management.

[Landslide risk assessment and management comprises the estimation of the level of risk, deciding whether or not it is acceptable, and exercising appropriate control

measures to reduce the risk when the risk level cannot be accepted (Ho et al., 2000). It requires the following issues to be addressed: (a) probability of landsliding, (b) runout behavior of landslide debris, (c) vulnerability of property and people to landslide, (d) landslide risk to property and people, and (e) management strategies and decision-making

5.2 Distributed landslide risk assessment

Distributed landslide risk assessment is aimed at providing a risk map that depicts the level of risk in terms of fatality or economic loss at different locations of a given region quantitatively or qualitatively. The spatial distribution of landslide risk may be obtained by spatial subdivision of the area under study and multiplication of spatial landslide probability, affected zones, land-use or spatial distribution of population or property, and vulnerability. This type of calculation can easily be calculated within the GIS (Leone et al., 1996). A priority ranking system for selection of slopes for detailed investigation and necessary upgrading, which can systematically ranks old slopes in an order of priority based on their probability of failure and the consequence of failure, is a commonly used empirical approach for risk assessment, based on an inventory database of all potentially unstable slopes in an area. For instance, the Geotechnical Engineering Office (GEO) of the Hong Kong Government established New Priority Classification Systems (NPCSSs) for slopes and retaining walls developed as part of the GEO Slope Information System (SIS), under which a total score can be calculated for soil cut slopes, rock cut slopes, fill slopes and retaining slopes, reflecting the relative risk of landslide involving the feature. The total score is obtained from the multiplication of an instability score and a consequence score. The instability score is based on an assessment of a number of key parameters that affect the likelihood of failure. The consequence score reflects the likely consequence of failure. The higher the total score, the higher the priority for follow-up action on the feature generally (Wong, 1998)

5.3 Site-specific landslide risk assessment

Site-specific risk assessment serves to provide a systematic assessment of the hazards and level of risk in terms of fatality (or economic loss, as appropriate) at a given site, or a potential landslide. This facilitates the consideration of whether the risk levels are acceptable and the evaluation of different risk mitigation measures, usually on the basis of cost–benefit analyses. In general, the event tree technique is well suited to a site-specific quantitative risk assessment given its greater degree of refinement. Once the probability of landsliding, runout behavior of landslide debris or elements at risk, and vulnerability terms have been derived, risk values may be simply obtained by Eqs. (1) or (2). Event-tree analysis can be used to quantify the risk from the potential failure. The procedure consists

of the following steps (Wu et al., 1996): Examine possible triggering factors, such as earthquakes or/and rainstorms; Identify possible failure modes; Estimate probability of failure for each failure mode; Evaluate runout behavior of landslide debris for each failure mode; Assess the risk for each failure mode; and Sum the risk for all possible failure modes.

5.4 Global landslide risk assessment

A global risk assessment, on the other hand, is aimed at defining the relative contribution to the total risk (e.g. number of fatalities per year), which can provide a reference for landslide risk management and consideration of resources allocation and policy-making. It can be calculated by summing site-specific risk of all slopes in the region under study.

5.5 Landslide risk management

Once the risk from a landslide or areas susceptible to or affected by landsliding are identified, measures may be taken to mitigate landslide risk to the community if necessary. The community faced with a landslide has a variety of strategies to deal with it, and these strategies may be grouped into planning control, engineering solution, acceptance, and monitoring and warning systems. Planning control may be seen as reducing expected elements at risk; the engineering solution strategy as reducing either the probability of landsliding or the probability of spatial impact of a landslide; the acceptance strategy as acceptable or unavoidable; and the monitoring and warning system strategy as reducing expected elements at risk by evacuation in advance of failure. The risks assessed as mentioned above can then be compared with the acceptance criteria to decide upon the landslide mitigation measures required.

5.6 Planning control

Planning control is one of the effective and economical ways to reduce landslide losses. It can be accomplished by (a) removing or converting existing development, and/or (b) discouraging or regulating new development in unstable areas (Kockelman, 1986). The latter option is the most economical and effective means for local governments if feasible. New developments can be prohibited, restricted or regulated in landslide-prone areas. Landslide-prone areas can be used as open space, parks, woodland and recreation, or specific land-uses or operations that might cause mass movement or that might be vulnerable to failure, such as irrigation, construction of roads and buildings, can be prohibited. excavation, grading, and construction regulations have been developed to ensure that construction in landslide prone area is planned and constructed in a manner that will not impair the stability of hillside slope

5.7 Engineering solution

Engineering solution is the most direct and costly strategy for reducing landslide risk. Two general approaches are available for mitigating landslide risk. One is correction of the underlying unstable slope to control initiation of landslides, and the other is controlling of the landslide movement.

5.7.1 Correction of the underlying unstable slope

The most commonly used remedial measures for correction of the underlying unstable slope are modification of the slope geometry by excavation or toe fill, drainage of surface and ground water, use of retaining structures, and internal slope reinforcement. These remedial measures are excellent site-specific management tools for landslides if correctly designed and constructed. The major negative aspect in their use is their high cost. For this reason, they are often used where landslide costs are very high because of high population densities and property values. Slope geometry modification by removal of all or part of the earth driving the landslide is the most efficient way of increasing the factor of safety of a slope.

Drainage is the most widely used method for slope stabilization. Underground drainage systems and pumping wells remove ground water and decrease pore water pressure, thus increasing the shear strength of soil. Surface water is drained from the unstable areas by surface ditches so as to reduce surface water infiltration into the potential slide mass. In the design of underground drainage systems to stabilize slopes, the capacity of each drain or outlet pipe should be accounted for. The underground drainage system should have the capacity to decrease pore water pressure at the failure surface in order to stabilize the landslide as much as possible. Slope stability can also be increased by placing retaining structures to increase the resistance to movement. These include gravity retaining walls, crib-block walls, gabion walls, passive piles, piers and caissons, cast-in situ reinforced concrete walls, reinforced earth-retaining structures with strip/sheetpolymer/metallic reinforcement elements, etc.

Generally, the following minimum information is required to determine the type and size of a restraining structure: (a) the boundaries and depth of the unstable area, its moisture content and its relative stability; (b) the type of landslide that is likely to develop or has occurred; and (c) the foundation conditions, since restraining structures require a satisfactory anchorage. In addition, the site conditions for construction may also affect the choice of retaining structures. Internal slope reinforcement is aimed at modifying the fundamental properties of in-situ slope soils to improve the internal

resistance against sliding by block bolts, micropiles, soil nailing, anchor, grouting with cement or chemicals, stone or lime/cement columns.

5.7.2 Controlling of the landslide movement

An alternative landslide risk-mitigating strategy of engineering solutions is to control the movement of landslide debris so as to reduce the spatial impact of landslides on downslope property. Traditional mitigation measures address landslide hazards through the installation of mechanical barriers where necessary to protect structures. The most frequently used designs include diversionary structures or levees to direct landslide debris into predetermined depositional areas, debris defenses intended to absorb kinetic energy, and retaining walls designed to withstand and/or deflect impacts [However, the volume of a potential landslide likely to impact a specific site should be estimated qualitatively or quantitatively. Knowledge of material properties of landslide debris and topography below the landslide site could be used to estimate the mass and velocity of landslide debris likely to impact a site as an input to the predictive models of runout distance outlined previously. Debris defenses on hillslopes below the landslide sources typically consist of a series of post set in concrete and connected by either wooden cross members or a chain-link fence. Such structures might decelerate small failures, but they are relatively ineffective on very steep slopes or for containing large failures, and thus should not be employed to protect structures (Montgomery et al., 1991). Retaining walls can be installed downslope of landslides to stop moving landslide debris. However, care should be taken to consider their effectiveness and economics because they are vulnerable to overtopping by either high velocity landslide debris or accumulated deposits from repeated events. As well, they are relatively expensive to build, requiring specific design considerations for both the volume and velocity of landslide events.

5.7.3 Monitoring and warning systems

Potentially unstable slopes can be monitored so that the potentially affected residents can be warned and, if necessary, evacuated. For specific landslides or potential slopes of such a large magnitude that stabilization works or engineering solutions were not only impracticable but would also not be cost-effective in relation to the property in risk, monitoring and landslide warning would be an alternative option to reduce landslide risk. The response of a particular slope when subjected to an earthquake is generally examined using the critical acceleration under which the slope would be brought to a state of limit equilibrium according to a pseudo-static analysis. When the acceleration imposed on the slope exceeds its critical acceleration, displacement or failure will result. A warning can be issued if an earthquake that can produce peak ground acceleration exceeding its critical acceleration can be predicted in advance

5.7.4. Acceptance

- A community may need to accept the risk from a given landslide under the condition that the risks are perfectly understood. The selection of this option is based on considerations that the risks from landslides are offset against the benefits which the community obtains in the particular locations, or that risks from landslides are tolerable [1]. Before the acceptance strategy is adopted, acceptable risk criteria should be established. [IUGS Working Group on Landslides, Committee on Risk Assessment (1997) defines the tolerable risk as a risk that society is willing to live with so as to secure certain benefits in the confidence that it is being properly controlled, kept under review and further reduced as and when possible, and provides the following general principles that can be applied when considering tolerable risk criteria.
- 1 The incremental risk from a hazard to an individual should not be significant compared to other risks to which a person is exposed in everyday life;
- The incremental risk from a hazard should, wherever reasonably practicable, be reduced, i.e. the As Low As Reasonably Practicable (ALARP) principle should apply;
- If the possible loss of life from a landslide incident is high, the risk that the incident might actually occur should be low. This accounts for the particular intolerance of a society to incidents that cause many simultaneous casualties, and is embodied in societal tolerance risk criteria;
- Persons in the society will tolerate higher risks than they regard as acceptable, when they are unable to control or reduce the risk because of financial or other limitations;
- Higher risks are likely to be tolerated for existing slopes than for planned projects, and for workers in industries with hazardous slopes, e.g. mines, than for society as a whole;
- Tolerable risks are higher for naturally occurring landslides than those from engineered slopes; Once a natural slope has been placed under monitoring, or risk mitigation measures have been executed, the tolerable risks approach those of engineered slopes;
- Tolerable risks may vary from country to country, and within countries, depending on historic exposure to landslide hazard, and the system of ownership and control of slopes and natural landslide hazards

CONCLUSION: Landslide risk assessment and management has led to the development of a new paradigm which demands a pluralistic approach to

risk assessment and risk management and for value-focused decision making. It embeds the use of science in risk assessment and risk management and landslide studies within a sociopolitical framework, and subsumes within the decision making process the nature of landslides and the nature of human activities. This is not to diminish the role of scientists and of engineers in decision-making in landslide hazard mitigation. On the contrary, the new paradigm relies crucially on a better understanding of landslide processes and on greater sophistication, transparency and rigor in the application of science, but within a collaborative and consensual decision-making framework. However, in the present knowledge, there are few reliable techniques available for assessing landslide hazard that is defined as the probability of occurrence of a given magnitude of failure.

Those available often require detailed geotechnical information on the existing conditions. Because of the high cost involved they are generally only achievable at the site investigation level in cases where high risk is anticipated. Probability of landsliding and runout behavior of landslide debris are more commonly assessed by historically based, largely stochastic analysis of precedents. The accuracy with which landslide probability can be determined thus depends largely on the length, quality and nature of the information record. Probability of occurrence can be determined either directly from landslide record or indirectly by establishing the landslide- triggering threshold of the initiating agent and analyzing agent behavior.

With both approaches, the minimum information requirements are a record of events including descriptions to characterize location, date, associated triggering conditions, causes, nature and length of warning, as well as landslide magnitude characteristics such as volume, material type and nature, and extent of runout. The main drawback of the precedent approach is the uncertainty associated with applying the findings to areas beyond where the precedence was established. For this reason or because there is insufficient record of past activity, hazard assessments are sometimes based on theoretically determined causative factors rather than on precedence. The outcome of this approach is the ranking of terrain susceptibility to landsliding. The validation of landslide susceptibility

mapping and its usefulness depends on the maintenance of appropriate records indicating the magnitude and frequency of on-going landslide activity and its relationship with terrain and triggering conditions. Although it is still only possible to predict slope failure in most general terms and virtually impossible to forecast the location, magnitude and timing of specific future events, regional scale landslide risk studies could result in the identification of tracts of land with different levels of hazard and risk. Such a hazard and risk zoning provides an ideal framework for land-use planning, development control, the application of building codes/ordinances, guidelines for engineering practice. At large and site-specific scales, landslide risk studies can provide the information necessary for decision-making. The process of landslide risk assessment and management depends on the completeness and quality of basic information on historic landslide data, and other physical and social data. In developing an inventory of all landslides in the area under study, one should determine the ages of different landslide deposits, with the aim of estimating recurrence intervals and determining risk where possible, and incorporate landslide trigger data, such as rainfalls and earthquakes, to establish time-frequency probabilities for single major storms and for highrainfall seasons. It is very clear that limited historic data often constrains the use of vulnerability assessment and risk analysis in land-use planning.

Conflicts of interest

No potential Conflict of interest was reported by the Authors.

Funding Statement

This study term paper written by our group and its only for study purpose. So we don't have any financial support .

Acknowledgements

Thanks to the teacher Shuqian Duan, Assistant professor, School of Civil Engineering, Zhengzhou University, for him constructive advices and all the group members.

References:

*distribution and risk control of landslides in China, induced by Runqiu Huang*²,

1. Journal of Rock Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering. 2011, [Formation, Weile Li, State Key Laboratory of Geohazards Prevention and Geoenvironment Protection, Chengdu University of Technology, Chengdu, 610059, China .Received 18 March 2011; received in revised form 8 May 2011; accepted 16 May 2011]
2. Geomatics, Natural Hazards and Risk, ISSN: 1947-5705 (Print) 1947-5713 (Online) Journal homepage: <https://www.tandfonline.com/loi/tgnh20> [Characteristics and mechanisms of coupled road and rainfall-induced landslide in Sichuan China, induced by Kun He, Guotao Ma, Xiewen Hu, Gang Luo, Xuefeng Mei, Bo Liu & Xingxiang He]
3. Spatiotemporal Distribution of Nonseismic Landslides during the Last 22 Years in Shaanxi Province, China.
Induced by Haijun Qiu, Yifei Cui, Dongdong Yang, Yanqian Pei, Sheng Hu, Shuyue Ma, Junqing Hao and Zijing Liu,
4. [Catena] journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/catena
Temporal patterns of nonseismically triggered landslides in Shaanxi Province, China, Induced by Haijun Qiu^{a,b,c,*}, Yifei Cui^d, Yanqian Pei^c, Dongdong Yang^c, Sheng Hu^c, Xingang Wang^e, Shuyue Ma^c.
Article in Catena · December 2019 DOI: 10.1016/j.catena.2019.104356
5. Landslides and Cropland Abandonment in China's Mountainous Areas: Spatial Distribution, Empirical Analysis and Policy Implications Induced by Xin Deng, Dingde Xu, Miao Zeng and Yanbin Qi
Received: 5 October 2018; Accepted: 25 October 2018; Published: 27 October 2010
6. Landslide risk assessment and management: an overview F.C. Dai^a, C.F. Lee^{b,*}, Y.Y. Ngai^b
Institute of Geographical Sciences and Natural Resources, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100101, China^b Department of Civil and Structural Engineering, The University of Hong Kong, Pokfulam Road, Hong Kong, China Received 21 December 2000; accepted 29 August 2001
7. 2010 China floods – Wikipedia https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/2010_China_floods.
8. CGEIS (2017) China geological environment information site. Bulletin of National Geological Hazards 2004–2016. <http://www.cigem.gov.cn>. Accessed 22 Feb 2017 (in

Chinese).

9. Yan R. Secondary disaster and environmental effect of landslide and collapsed dams in the upper reaches of Minjiang River. MS Thesis. Chengdu: Sichuan University, 2006 (in Chinese).

10. Huang R Q, Li W L. Fault effect analysis of geohazards triggered by Wechuan Earthquake. *Journal of Engineering Geology*, 2009